

Supplementary Material to “A DATA-DRIVEN FRAMEWORK FOR EMPIRICAL WILDFIRE DAMAGE ASSESSMENT OF BUILT INFRASTRUCTURE”

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BIN SIZE SELECTION FOR BUILDING DAMAGE PERCENTAGE AND DISTANCE

Figure S-1 shows the histograms of the number of exposed and destroyed buildings (on the left vertical axis) as functions of distance from burned vegetation, $d_{v,h}$, for three California fires—the Camp Fire (2018), the Tubbs Fire (2017), and the Carr Fire (2018). On the right vertical axis, this figure shows the percentage of destroyed buildings FDB when the DINS layer is used alone (with the legend ‘DINS only’) and when the proposed framework is applied to include uninspected buildings (with the legend ‘Proposed’). For FDB calculation, bins with less than 100 buildings were merged in all figures. The results are shown using two bin sizes of 50 m and 20 m. For each fire, it is observed that the trend for the percentage of destroyed buildings is similar for both values of the bin size; however, the percentage distribution is more stable in the case of the 50-m bin size, as noted by the reduced fluctuations in the point-to-point estimate. Based on this observation, a bin size of 50 m was used to present results related to $d_{v,h}$ in the rest of the study.

Figure S-2 shows the histograms of the number of exposed and destroyed buildings along with the fraction of destroyed buildings FDB as a function of the distance from the nearest burned structure, d_s , for the Camp, the Tubbs, and the Carr fires. As previously done for $d_{v,h}$, during the discretization of FDB , successive bins are merged when they have less than 100 buildings, and the FDB plot is terminated when less than 100 buildings are available despite merging of bins. Two values of bin size—10 m and 5 m—have been adopted to investigate the effect of bin sizes. Since the FDB value is relatively more stable for the 10 m bin size for each fire, this bin size was adopted to present results related to d_s in the rest of this study.

Fig. S-1. Histograms of number of exposed and destroyed buildings and percentage of destroyed buildings as functions of $d_{v,h}$ for the Camp, Tubbs, and Carr fires: (a, c, e) using bin sizes of 50 m; and (b, d, f) using bin sizes of 20 m.

Fig. S-2. Histograms of number of exposed and destroyed buildings and percentage of destroyed buildings as functions of d_s for Camp, Tubbs, and Carr fires: (a, c, e) using bin sizes of 10 m; and (b, d, f) using bin sizes of 5 m.

PARAMETRIC STUDY FOR INFLUENCE OF SAFE DISTANCES ON IGNITION MODE CLASSIFICATION AND FRACTION OF DESTROYED BUILDINGS

The ignition mode classification proposed in this study needs to assume specified values for the safe distance from burning vegetation, VSD_{rc} , and the safe distance from burning structures, SSD_{rc} . However, the values of these safe distances are not readily available in the literature. In this section, a sensitivity study is performed to investigate the impact of the assumed values of VSD_{rc} and SSD_{rc} on the ignition mode classification results. For both safe distances, the values of 20 m, 30 m, and 40 m are considered as plausible and used in this sensitivity analysis.

Tables S-1 presents the variation in the ignition mode contribution for vegetation radiant/contact mode (V-RC), $IMC_{V-R/C}$, for the Camp, Tubbs, and Carr fires. The table also shows the fraction of destroyed buildings $FDB_{V-R/C}$ in parentheses. By assuming the baseline values of both VSD_{rc} and SSD_{rc} equal to 30 m, the vegetation radiant/contact ignition mode contribution $IMC_{V-R/C}$ was found to be 4%, 3%, and 15% for the Camp, Tubbs, and Carr fires, respectively. When both safe distances are increased to 40 m, the $IMC_{V-R/C}$ values change to 2%, 3%, and 17% for the three fires, respectively; whereas when a smaller value of 20 m is used for both safety distances, $IMC_{V-R/C}$ values change to 9%, 2%, and 13% for the same three fires, respectively. It is noted that the effect of VSD_{rc} on $IMC_{V-R/C}$ is significantly smaller compared to that of SSD_{rc} . For example, in the Camp Fire, for $SSD_{rc} = 30$ m, changing VSD_{rc} to 40 m and 20 m results in minor changes of $IMC_{V-R/C}$ to 5% and 3%, respectively. By contrast, for a $VSD_{rc} = 30$ m, changing SSD_{rc} to 40 m and 20 m results in larger changes of $IMC_{N-R/C}$ to 2% and 11%, respectively.

Results for structure radiant/contact (S-R/C) and combined radiant/contact (C-R/C) ignition modes are provided in Tables S-2, and S-3, respectively. Similar to the case of V-R/C, IMC values are more sensitive to SSD_{rc} changes than to VSD_{rc} changes, for both S-R/C and C-R/C ignition modes.

Table S-1. Ignition mode contribution for vegetation radiant/contact mode $IMC_{V-R/C}$ with varying vegetation safe distance (VSD_{rc}) and structure safe distance (SSD_{rc}). The values of *fraction of destroyed buildings* for vegetation radiant/contact ignition mode ($FDB_{V-R/C}$) are shown in parentheses.

Fire	VSD_{rc}	SSD_{rc}		
		40 m	30 m	20 m
Camp	40 m	2% (78%)	5% (86%)	14% (92%)
	30 m	2% (83%)	4% (90%)	11% (94%)
	20 m	1% (87%)	3% (92%)	9% (96%)
Tubbs	40 m	3% (80%)	4% (81%)	5% (84%)
	30 m	2% (82%)	3% (81%)	4% (84%)
	20 m	1% (80%)	2% (81%)	2% (84%)
Carr	40 m	17% (52%)	20% (54%)	23% (57%)
	30 m	13% (57%)	15% (59%)	18% (62%)
	20 m	9% (61%)	11% (63%)	13% (65%)

Table S-2. Ignition mode contribution for structural radiant/contact mode $IMC_{S-R/C}$ with varying VSD_{rc} and SSD_{rc} . The values of *fraction of destroyed buildings* for structural radiant/contact ignition mode ($FDB_{S-R/C}$) are shown in parentheses.

Fire	VSD_{rc}	SSD_{rc}		
		40 m	30 m	20 m
Camp	40 m	69% (86%)	53% (89%)	21% (91%)
	30 m	73% (86%)	55% (89%)	22% (91%)
	20 m	76% (87%)	58% (89%)	23% (91%)
Tubbs	40 m	76% (81%)	66% (85%)	40% (86%)
	30 m	77% (81%)	67% (85%)	40% (86%)
	20 m	78% (81%)	67% (85%)	40% (86%)
Carr	40 m	45% (56%)	34% (63%)	11% (55%)
	30 m	47% (57%)	36% (64%)	12% (58%)
	20 m	50% (58%)	38% (65%)	13% (58%)

Table S-3. Ignition mode contribution for combined radiant/contact mode $IMC_{C-R/C}$ with varying VSD_{rc} and SSD_{rc} . The values of *fraction of destroyed buildings* for combined radiant/contact ignition mode ($FDB_{C-R/C}$) are shown in parentheses. The value of $IMC_{C-R/C}$ for the Tubbs Fire corresponding to $VSD_{rc} = 20$ m and $SSD_{rc} = 20$ m is 0.5%.

Fire	VSD_{rc}	SSD_{rc}		
		40 m	30 m	20 m
Camp	40 m	17% (96%)	14% (96%)	5% (96%)
	30 m	14% (97%)	11% (97%)	4% (97%)
	20 m	11% (97%)	9% (98%)	3% (97%)
Tubbs	40 m	3% (85%)	2% (85%)	1% (73%)
	30 m	2% (84%)	1% (87%)	1% (78%)
	20 m	1% (90%)	1% (93%)	0% (87%)
Carr	40 m	10% (80%)	7% (83%)	4% (89%)
	30 m	7% (80%)	5% (81%)	2% (84%)
	20 m	5% (82%)	3% (84%)	2% (88%)